

Möbius Book EPUB 3 Extension

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1. Introduction

The Möbius book needs an extension to the EPUB standard, which currently only allows to include one audio segment per text segment. To allow multiple audio segments, the standard needs a proprietary extension that must be reflected in the EPUB parser underlying the Möbius Player.

2. EPUB 3 Extension

The Möbius book needs an extension to the EPUB standard, which currently only allows to include one audio segment per text segment.

```
<smil xmlns="http://www.w3.org/ns/SMIL" xmlns:epub="http://www.idpf.org/2007/ops"
version= 3.0">

<body>

<seq id="seq000001" epub:textref="Section0001.xhtml">

<par id="par000001">

<text src="Section0001.xhtml#f000"/>

<audio src="../../Audio/bosporus_vox.mp3" clipBegin="00:00:13.000" clipEnd="00:00:15.480"/>

</par>

<par id="par000002">

<text src="Section0001.xhtml#f001"/>

<audio src="../../Audio/bosporus_vox.mp3" clipBegin="00:00:15.480" clipEnd="00:00:19.040"/>

</par>

</seq>

</body>
```

To allow multiple audio segments, the standard needs a proprietary extension. This extension needs to be reflected in the EPUB parser underlying the Möbius Player.

```
<smil xmlns="http://www.w3.org/ns/SMIL" xmlns:epub="http://www.idpf.org/2007/ops"
version= 3.0">

<body>

<seq id="seq000001" epub:textref="Section0001.xhtml">

<par id="par000001">

<text src="Section0001.xhtml#f000"/>

<audio layer="nar" src="vox.mp3" clipBegin="00:00:13.000" clipEnd="00:00:15.480"/>

<audio layer="sfx" spatial="true" src="sfx.mp3" clipBegin="00:00:13.000"
clipEnd="00:00:15.480"/>

<audio layer="mus" src="music.mp3" clipBegin="00:00:13.000" clipEnd="00:00:15.480"/>

</par>

<par id="par000002">

<text src="Section0001.xhtml#f001"/>

<audio layer="nar" src="vox.mp3" clipBegin="00:00:15.480" clipEnd="00:00:19.040"/>

<audio layer="sfx" src="sfx.mp3" clipBegin="00:00:13.000" clipEnd="00:00:15.480"/>

<audio layer="mus" src="music.mp3" clipBegin="00:00:13.000" clipEnd="00:00:15.480"/>

</par>

</seq>

</body>

</smil>
```

By using the same tag names, we make sure that conventional EPUB parsers can still parse the format (they'll typically ignore the additional ones). The "layer" attributes help the Player to distinguish the type of layer. The "spatial" tag lets the player know that the audio is in ambisonic format.

